

**Martin Paul Eve,
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Sharing research, not hoarding it

– Martin Eve

Open access to books enables more people to access and contribute to research. It encourages diversity of voices and thinking. And it makes the world a more equitable, knowledgeable place.

Knowledge and research should be at our fingertips. So says Martin Paul Eve, Professor of Literature, Technology and Publishing at Birkbeck, University of London. The technology exists to make research easily and freely available, but there are barriers that prevent it from happening on a wide scale.

Barriers to access

As someone with lived experience of access barriers – Eve has significant health and mobility issues which make it difficult for him to travel to libraries – Eve knows what a difference it makes when research is available digitally, free of cost.

Open access removes barriers. This doesn't just benefit people with disabilities. It benefits other people who also struggle to travel to libraries, such as those with caring responsibilities or financial constraints.

When access is denied, it impacts on individuals and the dissemination of research, says Eve.

He added:

“Knowledge doesn’t benefit anyone if it’s inaccessible. If things were openly accessible on the Internet, my life in research terms would be so much better.”

The North-South divide

Even many libraries can’t afford to pay for expensive books or subscription costs. This is particularly true of libraries in the Global South. Eve says this disadvantages scholars in places such as Africa.

Eve explained:

“Their work has been massively hindered by the fact they can’t get access to the same resources, but they’re still held to exactly the same standards of scholarship as everybody else. It also means research generally has less diversity and breadth of thinking.”

Good access improves research

When academics can access a diverse range of materials, it encourages speculative reading and the deeper exploration of ideas. It also facilitates scholarly ways of working. Eve said:

“ The easier you make it to check what someone has said and how they’re using a reference, the more inclined people will be to do it and the more rigorous their scholarly practices will end up being. Research is not finding or having access to material. It’s reading it, engaging with it, synthesising it and building on it.

Open access also fosters experimentation, inviting people to explore different outputs with their own research or other people’s – new formats, interactive elements and translation, for example.

The fear factor

Fear holds a lot of people back. Many academics view open access books as less prestigious and less impactful.

Eve says it couldn’t be further from the truth. He was awarded the Philip Leverhulme Prize for Literary Studies in 2019 and put that money into publishing his work open access. Without the prize, publishing open access would have been a lot harder for Eve as his university does not have the funds to give grants very easily. He has

published 10 books open access and has very high citation figures and a very high profile. He said:

“ It’s had a very positive impact on my career. And I have much greater satisfaction and purpose in what I do, knowing there’s a much broader audience for my work. People who don’t engage with open access are missing out on a huge opportunity to do good in the world.

Over time, Eve thinks more and more academics will switch to open access, when they realise it will improve their reader and citation numbers. While those who close themselves off only reach a limited audience, diminishing their impact.